

Talking AI into Being: The Imaginaries of National AI Strategies and their Performative Politics

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Facing the current rush towards artificial intelligence (AI) by private tech companies such as Google, Facebook, Baidu or Alibaba and current public media attention for the subject, governments around the globe have proclaimed to partake in a global AI race. During the past four years national AI strategies have been popping up all around the globe, identifying potentials and risks that go along AI development, leapfrogging AI research through huge sums of investments and proclaiming the aim to steer AI future through policy measures.

In the present paper we identify these national AI policy papers as a peculiar hybrid between policy and discourse. They are at the same time tech policy, national strategic positioning and an imaginary of public goods. Conceptually the paper is informed by the the sociology of expectations, socio-technical imaginaries and myths. Empirically we analyse the socio-technical narratives articulated by AI policy documents of four key players in the field, namely China, USA, France and Germany. The discourse analysis of the documents' rhetoric and argumentative structures show how contested and vague policy documents establish a seemingly inevitable technological pathway towards AI deployment across almost every societal sector. Although the final imagined socio-technical orders differ across the compared countries, we identify the following themes that serve as shared building blocks in the process of AI imaginary construction in all four countries:

- (1) Situating AI in a grand historical legacy of technological progress and celebrating a **“revolutionary” AI break-through moment**, the strategy papers (re)create a myth of determinist technological development, and ascribe agency to a technology that “befalls” our societies.
- (2) Talk about an undecipherable AI future opens **a window of uncertainty which invites for clarification and leadership intervention**. National leaders coin uncertainty into an opportunity to take initiative and to mobilise societal attention in order to co-produce the very futures they envision.
- (3) **AI Socio-technological imaginaries as a projection of political culture**: The national AI visions unravel different national idealizations of social life and social order. Deconstructing the call for leadership we identify visions of collectively desired lifestyles that are projected onto AI technology.
- (4) **Locked in path dependencies**. Socio-technological imaginaries materialise in the drafting of policies, the mobilisation of industries and the allocation of resources. Thus, the imaginaries are not only be understood as constitutive but as performative: they create situations of irreversibility as investments ask for return and political promises have to be met.

Notwithstanding the obvious differences between the substance of national AI strategies, this analysis identifies a surprising consistency in the narrative construction of the AI imaginaries. As societies and policy struggle to keep up with the perceived dynamic changes, the AI pathway seems to constitute a particular worrisome example of technology-driven, over-hyped development, that is rather fuelled by idealisations, projections and myths around AI than by normative and political reflections on how to serve public welfare.